

HOW TO IMPROVE LISTENING SKILLS FOR ESL STUDENTS?

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ABSTRACT

In this article, we will teach ESL students how to understand English speech by ear, how to choose and listen to a podcast appropriate to the topic and level of English, the usefulness of listening lessons, how to learn English correctly from audio materials, what podcasts are, detailed information about the term ESL is given.

ESL - this term refers to English as a second language and requires students to be taught English in countries where English is the main language of communication. Canada, the United Kingdom, the United States, Australia, etc. fall into this category, where English is spoken everywhere, but students learning English are of different nationalities. These students must be fluent in English to meet the requirements of education and employment.

When learning English, many face difficulties in understanding and listening to English. In addition, the person can read and write perfectly without error.

Learning English can be relatively easy in some ways. For example, memorizing vocabulary or learning grammar are issues that can be easily

learned with consistency. However, learning to understand the words of others is not at all easy to know by listening to words called Listening.

Listening to English is one of the key skills in the whole foreign language learning process. Listening encourages a person to speak, that is, develops another basic skill - speech.

The most important thing to remember is that listening to English is a skill, and the task for the requirements is to develop it.

The only way to develop hearing ability is to teach the listener to differentiate and understand the words in a sentence.

To improve ESL students' listening in English, they must first learn the techniques of working with text.

The following guidelines will help you work with text and develop listening skills:

1. Students should always listen. Even if students are very busy, they should take time to listen for 30 minutes a day. The main thing here is regularity.
2. Before students start listening, they need to adjust the performance, they need to separate the world, concentration is the most necessary detail. Students should promise themselves that in the next 30 minutes, they will only practice their listening skills.

Hearing ability is the ability to hear and understand English. Listening is one of the basic skills of learning English.

Once a student begins to learn English, he or she must select texts for listening that are appropriate for the level of knowledge of that language.

Once the student has stopped working with the text, he or she can listen to many audio and video tutorials in the foreign language, such as dialogues, thematic texts, and audio stories, in order to master the ability to listen and speak fluently in a foreign language. should listen to them again.

This is the main reason why audio books in English are so popular among students. The more they listen, the faster they become accustomed to foreign speech and begin to understand it. And given that most free audiobooks are spoken by non-professional native language

experts, they can also listen to people with different pronunciations. Someone whispers, someone makes vague sounds, someone speaks too fast - it's a great exercise for your listening ability.

If students really want to learn, they must listen to English every day. We all know that this is the most important step needed to develop a student's listening ability. Listening to the English language used allows you to learn more about its natural use.

The main way to develop English language skills through active listening is to listen to conversational topics from a variety of sources. This then introduces students to unfamiliar dictionaries and broader accents.

ESL students need to develop a strategy in a specific direction. This strategy should have a step-by-step tracking system.

ESL students who are learning English should not lose focus when listening to any audio for their own benefit.

One of the biggest challenges for students learning a language is speaking it, working it out loud. The main reason is embarrassment or embarrassment for saying something wrong and an inability to think about what to say in the first place.

But there is no better way to learn a language than to speak it, as they can learn countless words and, if they wish, must memorize an English dictionary completely. If the students are never practicing it, if they don't speak the same language to other people, it will be difficult for them to use it when they need to.

As we have said many times about listening, students can find the best learning tool to listen to songs and audios because the brain is ready to memorize the lyrics of the songs without the person having to feel them. When they listen to a song, they like it over and over again. This is something that is done automatically, even before you speak.

Listening Rules:

- 1) Students listen to the audio recording a maximum of 2 times and try to understand the main meaning of what is being said.
- 2) Each student reads the text of the audio recording and analyzes each word in detail, using dictionaries if necessary.
- 3) The student likes the audio recording again and listens to it again based on the text, pausing in places that are difficult to understand.

It is very important to listen carefully to the pronunciation of each phrase, to compare it with its analogue in the text in order to understand how to pronounce it.

- 4) The final step is to listen to the writing without relying on the text to reinforce the material.
- 5) If this is the case, then the final stage can be a stage of performing various tasks related to the text, which is better to do without relying on it.

When a student chooses audio recordings, of course, they have to choose according to their level. We encourage teachers to select podcasts based on their level to improve this skill.

1. The student must choose the right level of interesting material

2. You need to find the best way to work with the podcast

In their spare time, language learners can listen to audio recordings or use other tactics:

- Listen to the audio material and try to understand as much information as possible from it. If this is difficult, try to understand the main message of the post.
- Find, read the text of a message and translate phrases they do not know.
- Turn on the sound again and try to listen to the text they know.
- Tell your friends, family, or yourself what you have heard in the mirror, trying to imitate the speaker's speech.

This tactic does not seem to take much time. The student spends only 15-20 minutes analyzing the five-minute audio material.

The reader is also involved in the order in which these processes are performed

The main tasks of the teacher in the class are:

- Listening to a variety of listening comprehension tasks to engage the learner, drawing attention and knowing the vocabulary before listening;
- listening assistance - teaching to listen to important moments and the information they need while listening and removing difficulties in paying attention to some;
- Listening, after the hearing, as well as the conclusions after the hearing, not only to

strengthen the audit, but also to verify that there was a reason for the audit.

In fact, it is better to start learning a foreign language at a very young age. As the brain activity of young children continues to develop steadily, they are able to absorb new information much faster than adults, whose brain activity is fully formed. It is advisable to plan the lesson taking into account these features. For example, the use of games, pictures, songs, poems, and cartoons is an effective way to teach a foreign language to preschool children.

During the audition, students will be able to:

- find out what we are talking about at the scene;
- pay attention to what is unclear and raises questions about it;
- determination or denial obtained during the hearing;
- It is necessary to draw conclusions and bring.

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